

Drwencke, Adcock, Walker, and Tucker *“Use of an ethanol cornual nerve block as a long-term analgesic for disbudding of dairy calves: Two pilot studies”*



Supplemental Figure S1. Examples of injection site swelling that occurred after administration of an ethanol cornual nerve block.



Supplemental Figure S2. An example of a calf where no injection has been given and no swelling is present.